

Renewable Energy Cyber Security Forum

6th - 7th June 2023
Berlin, Germany

For further information on speaker & delegates opportunities, please contact:
John Isaac / email: johni@leadventgrp.com

Who Should Attend

Presidents, VPs, Directors, Heads, Managers, Engineers

- Information Security
- Cyber Security
- Digitalization
- Quality
- Scada
- Operational Technology
- Information Technology
- Risk
- Zero Trust
- Data
- Digital Information

Confirmed Speakers

Kim Elman
Director Center
for Cyber Security
RISE Research Institutes
of Sweden

Ayat-allah Bouramdane
Group Leader
"Climate Change –
– Energy"
Green Energy Park (GEP), Re-
search Institute
for Solar Energy
and New Energies
(IRESEN)

Troels Rahbek Lindhard
Lead Consultant
Peak Wind

Agis Digkas
Vice-President of BoD
Renewable Energy
Sources Operator
& Guarantees
of Origin – DAPEEP SA

Toni Michel Georg
Senior UX Researcher – Renew-
able Energy
Siemens Gamesa

Lisa Holmes
Head
of Information Security
Corre Energy

Richard Knowlton
Director
of Security Studies
Oxford cyber academy

Sachan Manish
Cyber Security Lead
Wood Plc

Florian Lütticken
Team Lead OT
Renewable Generation
EnBW – Energie Baden –
– Württemberg AG

Toralf Nitsch
CEO
GE4ABV

Stuart Okin
Deputy Director
for Cyber Regulation
& Digital Services
Ofgem

Mihai Mladin
Head of Projects Department
Romanian Energy Center

Jordi Cuijarro
CyberSecurity
Innovation Director
Fundació i2CAT
Panayiotis Nicolaides
Project & Maintenance
Engineer
Green Energy Group

Brijesh Suryawanshi
Lead Data Engineer
ORE Catapult

Carlo Corsaro
MLOps Lead
H2Go Power

Alexandru Mitea
Co-Founder & CEO
Green Energy Allies

Zoya Pourmirza
Senior Research Associate
Newcastle University

Shikhar Manocha
Technical Project Manager
Promondis Energy GmbH

Silvia Richard
Partner and Country Director
CONEXIG

Anjos Nijk
Managing Director
European Network
for Cyber Security
(ENCS)

Neda Maria Kaizumi
VP Quality
& Business Excellence
Freyr Clean Battery
Solutions

Paul Jenkinson
Cyber Security, IT Strategy
and Architecture Director
RES Renewable Norden Ab

Frank Brech
CEO
EnBW Cyber Security GmbH

Toni Sulankivi
Head of Cyber Security
Tiko Energy Solutions

Nikolaos Anagnostou
Senior Asset Performance Engi-
neer
Glennmont
Partners

River Providence
Founder and Director
Crown Green
Energy Services

Shahid Raza
Director
of Cyber Security Unit
RISE Research Institutes
of Sweden

Stefan Deutscher
Partner and Associate Director,
Global Topic Leader
for Cybersecurity & IT
Infrastructure Operations
Boston Consulting Group

**Renewable Energy
Cyber Security Forum**

**6th - 7th June 2023
Berlin | Germany**

Tuesday 6th June 2023

08:30 Chairman's Opening Remarks and Address

ENABLING A SECURE FUTURE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY MARKET

08:40 Opening Keynote

Looking to the Future – What Can we Expect to see in the Cybersecurity Ecosystem in 2023?

- A year in review: What cybersecurity advancements proved worthwhile?
- What progression in cybersecurity tech should we expect next year?
- What will be the role of technologies like Automation, AI and Machine Learning?

Panelists

David Stubbley / Managing Director, Cyber Security Services / 7 Elements Ltd

Anjos Nijk / Managing Director / European Network for Cyber Security (ENCS)

Kim Elman / Director Center for Cyber Security / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Troels Rahbek Lindhard / Lead Consultant / Peak Wind

09:05 Case Study

Renewable Energy vs. Energy Security

- How can renewable energy improve energy security?
- How to guarantee renewable energy supply despite climate change impacts on nature resources availability?
- The improvements in the renewable energy production and management to address energy security
- Some examples of the improvement of renewable energy production to guarantee energy security in Europe

Silvia Richard / Partner and Country Director / CONEXIG

09:30 Case Study

Cyber Security Threat Landscape 2023

- From highly capable advanced persistent threats, through to opportunistic and untargeted attacks using commonly available exploit code, this talk will take a look at the cyber threat landscape in 2023
- Drawing upon real life incidents covering complex ransomware attacks to business email compromise campaigns, David will demystify the often overly hyped field of cyber security.
- The talk will finish with mitigation advice that can be deployed by any organisation to reduce the risk of a successful compromise.

David Stubbley / Managing Director, Cyber Security Services / 7 Elements Ltd

09:55 Case Study

Cyber Security in the Future Energy System

- How RISE works with cross-disciplinary cyber security approaches
- Security implications of a green energy system
- Initiatives to support a cyber secure future energy system

Kim Elman / Director Center for Cyber Security / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

10:20 Case Study

How to Manage Vulnerabilities in the Renewable Energy Environment

- Why cyber security is important today on renewable energy assets?
- How cyber security will impact the renewable energy market?
- How to build cyber-safe and resilient renewable energy systems?
- What will be the role of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning?

Ayat-allah Bouramdane / Group Leader "Climate Change – Energy" / Green Energy Park (GEP), Research Institute for Solar Energy and New Energies (IRESEN)

10:45 Case Study

Making Cyber Security Operational

There is a wide acceptance that cyber security is an important topic, and a general tendency is to focus on the technology and rules for what you can and cannot do. Cyber security teams often end up as being perceived as police officers setting requirements and processes for the organisation and requiring new expensive hardware and software. But how do you engage the organisation in security?

- What are the key selling points in getting your organisation onboard the journey?
- Balancing security requirements with operational requirements
- Moving from security-oriented focus to solution-oriented focus

Troels Rahbek Lindhard / Lead Consultant / Peak Wind

11:10 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

11:40 Case Study

Renewable energy sources & modern technology challenges

- The rise of Mega-cities and their new energy needs
- Compensating renewable energy with new technology tools
- Blockchain and PPAs

Agis Digkas / Vice-President of BoD / Renewable Energy Sources Operator & Guarantees of Origin – DAPEEP SA

REGULATION AND POLICY, ORGANISING CYBER SECURITY ACROSS THE RENEWABLE SECTOR

12:05 Case Study

Cyber Regulation and how it is changing the Energy Sector

- Overview of regulation
- How the Network & Information Systems Regulation is driving change
- Lessons learned and areas we need to focus on

Stuart Okin / Deputy Director for Cyber Regulation & Digital Services / Ofgem

12:30 Case Study

4 steps in getting your Governance Right when starting a Renewable Energy company

1. **Accepting the risk**
 - a. Why risk acceptance isn't scary and can benefit your cyber security?
 - b. What is risk acceptance in Cyber Security?
 - c. Ways to accurately evaluate risk
2. **Cyber Security, why it is a bigger responsibility**
 - a. Understanding that Cyber Security is in everything
 - b. Why accepting the responsibility makes you prosper financially?
3. **The bigger picture of cyber security**
 - a. Dealing with and understanding the bigger picture
 - b. how to instill that culture against very disparate stakeholders
 - c. Manage stakeholders both externally and internally
4. **Why is Cyber Security important and critical to renewable energy operations?**
 - a. Why is the renewable energy industry different?
 - b. What are the threats?
 - i. Emerging markets, lots of firsts
 - c. How to mitigate or eliminate the risk
 - d. Buy in and instilling that Culture of Care (towards security) and the benefits it brings

Lisa Holmes / Head of Information Security / Corre Energy

12:55 Lunch Time Break

13:55 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

ACHIEVING EFFICIENCY AND EXCELLENCE IN CYBER SECURITY

14:05 Case Study

How Behavioral Science can Improve Security Behaviors?

- 95% of cyber-attacks succeed because of human action. That may seem like a high figure, but it's supported by a lot of surveys over several years. And of course we also know just how much effort hackers put into targeting people: it's just so much easier and cost-effective than trying to attack technology. How can we train people to follow security best practice? In cyber terms, how do we stop people clicking on a malicious link, or doing something else that ignores the rules? New advances in behavioral psychology suggest some possible new approaches to managing these issues.

Richard Knowlton / Director of security studies / Oxford cyber academy

14:30 Case Study

Managing Cyber Security Threats in the Renewal Energy Ecosystem.

- Threats and Vulnerabilities introduced by new technology
- Cost of Cyber Threats
- Cyber Security Strategies
- Countermeasures and Solutions

Christie Ogubere / Cyber Security Consultant / Innovation Centre

RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT

14:55 Case Study

Cyber Security Risks

- Renewable Systems Interconnection & Smart grid
- Renewable Systems Interconnection
- Trends Causing Increased Risk
- Cyber Security at:
 - The component level
 - The generation level
 - The interconnected levels
 - The control systems
 - How to fit?

Neda Maria Kaizumi / VP Quality & Business Excellence / Freyr Clean Battery Solutions

15:20 Case Study

Risk Assessment and Management

Security analytics is a data science backed cloud native platform that predicts, detects and prevents breaches. A risk-prioritized proactive analytics model gives you a comprehensive contextual view of entities behaviors to mitigate the most serious threats in your environment before internal or external cyberattacks can inflict damage.

Technologies

- Machine Learning Based Behavior Analytics
- Threat Modeling Automation
- Security as a Service (SaaS)

Applications

- Active Risk-Response Systems
- Intelligent Threat Hunting
- Analytics-driven cloud SIEM and Intelligent SOAR

Jordi Cuijarro / CyberSecurity Innovation Director / Fundació i2CAT

15:45 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

CYBERSECURITY ECOSYSTEM FOR A RESILIENT RENEWABLE ENERGY FUTURE

16:15 Case Study

Establishing an OT Organization as basis for a Resilient Cyber Security

- The emancipation of OT from IT and how this can strengthen cyber security.
- Why is an OT organization needed in parallel to IT?
- What role does information security play in shaping it?
- What is the interaction between IT and OT?
- What are the challenges of the future?

Jointly presented by

Florian Lütticken / Team Lead OT Renewable Generation / EnBW – Energie Baden – Württemberg AG

Frank Brech / CEO / EnBW Cyber Security GmbH

16:40 Case Study

Cyber Resilience in Renewable Energy: What stays the same, what changes, what to do about it?

- The paradigm shift from cybersecurity to cyber resilience
- Similarities with, and reusable established concepts from protecting traditional energy infrastructure
- Differences, needs, and opportunities to adapt to renewable energy infrastructures
- Challenges and bottlenecks of that transition

Stefan Deutscher / Partner and Associate Director, Global Topic Leader for Cybersecurity & IT Infrastructure Operations / Boston Consulting Group

17:05 Case Study

How we have Tackled the Possibility of Cyber-attacks on our Solar Farms?

The development of Solar parks in Cyprus, is in moving with very rapid pace. However, with the evolution of the digital technology, it would make sense for our parks to move towards the digital era. This involves digital energy meters, digital communication and measurements and even remote control of key components of the park.

Until today we have been using the method called port forwarding to forward out parks IP addresses, using public IP's. This method is highly used in Europe but can pose very low resistance towards hackers.

A new way to overcome this would be to use VPN servers along with firewalls to enable IP encryption and firewall systems that can enable to view specific equipment remotely, by using a Static IP address.

What the speech will include:

1. Advantages and disadvantages of port forwarding.
2. Advantages and disadvantages of using VPN connections in solar parks.
3. What we believe can be the next step in securing the solar parks even further.

Panayiotis Nicolaidis / Project & Maintenance Engineer / Green Energy Group

17:30 Panel Discussion

Let's Recap - How to Develop a Cyber Security Roadmap for your REN Assets

Are you placing the necessary controls in place to enable your business to remain efficient under attack? Are you able to develop a cyber security roadmap from scratch to secure your assets and have your C-level buy in? This roundtable discussion will help you navigate the complexities of cyber security and what steps you should be taking to develop a roadmap which enables your current infrastructure to be more secure and ultimately reduce risks for your business.

We'll be looking at how you can:

- Look at your technical gaps
- Segmentate your infrastructure
- Efficiently upgrade firewalls and log in events
- Educate your stakeholders by creating value for them
- Thinking about risks in terms of severity, likelihood, and the impact downstream
- Find the expertise you need by getting an assessment from standard bodies
- Looking at talent and skill set and why you should use unconventional Channels
- Sharing information on threats and collaborate in other ways to improve cyber resiliency

18:10 Chairman's Closing Remarks and End of Day One

Wednesday 7th June 2023

08:30 Chairperson Opening Remarks

ENABLING CYBERSECURITY IN THE AGE OF ASSET DIGITALIZATION

08:40 Case Study

AI and Automation Driven Approach towards Cyber Security in Renewable Energy

There are too many unpredictable variables like environmental factors in renewable energy generation which can pose as limitations for human decision making, AI and automation can not only help in optimization but also reducing the human error factor. Human errors are a leading cause of cyber security incidents in any organization, thereby reducing it reduces risks of cyber security incidents. Similar to OT closed loop control we need to have a closed loop automation in Cyber Security Solution. Closed loop cyber security solution is AI driven, autonomous, quick to respond and resolves the cyber security incidents without human intervention. Renewable ecosystem is fragmented to smaller units and places, which requires uniformly addressing the cyber resilience across all locations.

Sachan Manish / Cyber Security Lead / Wood Plc

09:05 Case Study

Cyber Security in the Cloud Environment

- What is cloud computing?
- Is it 'safe'?
- What cybersecurity threats are hiding inside the cloud?
- How can we deal with them?
- How Azure is being used to manage security in the projects managed by ORE Catapult.

Brijesh Suryawanshi / Lead Data Engineer / ORE Catapult

09:30 Case Study

Cyber Security in AI-based Hydrogen System Management

- Cyber security risks in hydrogen systems
- Vulnerability management in AI-powered autonomous systems
- Strategies for the detection and mitigation of cyber attacks

Carlo Corsaro / MLOps Lead / H2Go Power

09:55 Case Study

CYBERSEAS Project – Cyber Securing Energy dAta Services

- Countering the cyber risks related to highest impact attacks against EPES (Electrical Power and Energy Systems).
- Protecting consumers against personal data breaches and attacks.
- Increasing the security of the Energy Common Data Space.

Mihai Mladin / Head of Projects Department / Romanian Energy Center

10:20 Case Study

Cybersecurity in Renewables – An Asset Owner's Perspective

- How an asset owner looks at cybersecurity risks
- What can be done to manage such risks
- What are the key issues and pain points from our experience
- Digitisation and cybersecurity

Nikolaos Anagnostou / Senior Asset Performance Engineer / Glennmont Partners

10:45 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

11:15 Interactive Panel Discussion

Renewable Energy Cyber Security in the Age of Digitalization

- Why is it important and critical to renewable energy operations?
- Cybersecurity - emerging threats and strategies to address them.
- What cyber security issues emerge as digital strategies are adopted.
- Cybersecurity best practices for renewable energy.
- Building the next wave of cybersecurity capability

Panelists

Nikolaos Anagnostou / Senior Asset Performance Engineer / Glennmont Partners

Mihai Mladin / Head of Projects Department / Romanian Energy Center

Sachan Manish / Cyber Security Lead / Wood Plc

ENHANCING CYBER SECURITY RESILIENCE TO ENSURE A GREEN AND NET ZERO FUTURE

11:55 Case Study

Cyber Security in Energy Systems Digitalisation for Net Zero transition

The UK net zero target proposes to reduce 100% of the UK greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 (compared to 1990 levels), and digital technologies will play an important role to achieve this target. While digitalisation supports decentralisation and decarbonisation of energy systems by enabling more penetration of distributed energy resources and allowing services such as Demand Side Response, it can cause issues such as Cyber Security challenges. This talk will summarise cyber security challenges within digitalised energy system in the UK, and solutions to tackle these challenges.

Zoya Pourmirza / Senior Research Associate / Newcastle University

12:20 Case Study

The UNDP ITM Smart facility model - How combining cybersecurity and renewable energy solutions is a necessity in addressing sustainable development challenges.

- Presentation of Smart facility model and a case application
- Best practice in implementing smart facility solutions
- Finding common ground: Necessity of coordination between Smart Infrastructure Connectivity and Green Energy Teams

Moe Kyaw / Manager, Global Connectivity Support / UNDP – SIS Unit

THE FUTURE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY CYBERSECURITY

12:45 Case Study

Rethinking Renewable Energy Cybersecurity and Confidence in a Connected World

- Looking ahead: Cyber security and future technologies
- Is cyber on the board's agenda?
- Navigating rising cyber risks safely
- Cyber awareness: Key Insights and Practices
- Rethinking cybersecurity from the human element point of view

Toni Michel Georg / Senior UX Researcher – Renewable Energy / Siemens Gamesa

13:10 Lunch Time Break

14:10 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

14:20 Case Study

Building Defensible Architectures - Case Example VPP (Virtual Power Plant)

- There is no 100% security, aim for resilience, survivability, and recoverability.
- What does this mean for the Edge, Network Connectivity and Central IT Infrastructure?
- How to avoid common pitfalls in building your Cyber Strategy?

Toni Sulankivi / Head of Cyber Security / Tiko Energy Solutions

14:45 Case Study

Renewable Energy and National Security in Small Island States

- o State of the market
- o Barriers, threats, and opportunities for reducing risk
 - Barriers
 - Types of threats
- o Current trends in RE cyber security relevant to SIDs
- o Easily implementable solutions at different technological levels
 - Generation
 - Distribution
 - Grid Integration etc
- o Next steps for SIDs
 - Risk assessments and threat characterisation
 - Development of Policies and Procedures
- Implementation of systems in tandem with policy development

River Providence / Founder and Director / Crown Green Energy Services

15:10 Case Study

Cyber Threats within the Renewable Energy Sector

- Potential Threat Actors associated with the energy sector
- What makes the energy sector vulnerable to cyber security
- Examples of past attacks on energy sector and what we have learned
- How to combat these attacks

Gurpreet Thathy / Director of Cyber Security and Electronic Counter Measures / Valkyrie GB Ltd

15:35 Case Study

Cyber Security in Renewable Asset Management

- Discussion on the importance of cyber security for renewable energy assets
- Role of Smart grids and IoT solutions
- Assessing cyber security threats
- Response and Recovery planning capabilities of asset managers

Shikhar Manocha / Technical Project Manager / Promondis Energy GmbH

16:00 One-to -One Meetings & Networking Break

PROTECTING AND SECURING RENEWABLE ASSET

16:30 Case Study

Securing Digital Infrastructure for Renewable Energy – Challenges and Opportunities

Future energy systems will be a connected digital infrastructure of renewable sources. Distributed generation and distribution of energy would require interconnections not just between renewable energy sources and systems but also other sectors such as finance, automotive, and smart homes. Cybersecurity will be utmost important for the realization and success of such a digital infrastructure of interconnected IoT/OT devices, networks, computing edges and clouds, as well as processing and storing of sensitive and personal data. This talk will discuss the opportunities/solutions and challenges of securing a digital infrastructure for renewable energy. It will also highlight how the cybersecurity of such a complex digital infrastructure can be tested in a virtualized testbed, so called cyber range.

Shahid Raza / Director of Cyber Security Unit / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

16:45 Case Study

Cybersecurity – Protecting your Renewable Assets

- Industry trends and biggest risks
- How to manage your Cyber Security Strategy and good practice
- Case study and learnings

Paul Jenkinson / Cyber Security, IT Strategy and Architecture Director / RES Renewable Norden Ab

17:10 Case Study

Wind/Solar Resource Data

- The relevance of secured communications for Wind and Solar resource assessment and monitoring
- Data Integrity as a must to ensure bankability
- How to implement a secure data management solution

Mario Lopez / CEO / Albitel

17:35 Case Study

Securing our DER Resources

- Risk analysis – facts and fiction
- Chain security – who are risk owners?
- Best practices

Anjos Nijk / Managing Director / European Network for Cyber Security (ENCS)

18:00 Case Study

Blockchain as a Base for Renewable Energy Investments

- Green energy is not accessible to small players
- Fractioning renewable energy facilities
- Incentivize secure investments with blockchain solution
- Role of blockchain in fractioning of assets

Alexandru Mitea / Co-Founder & CEO / Green Energy Allies

18:25 Case Study

Blockchain Solar & The Power of the Many

- Blockchain and Photovoltaics - The Re-Invention of Democracy?
- Security and Trust - the Basics of the Peoples Power
- Web3 - Bringing the Energy to the point of Information
- AI and the Inspiration of the Masses

Toralf Nitsch / CEO / GE4ABV

18:50 Panel Discussion

Preparing Your Cyber Security Strategies Already Today

- How the future energy world will look like and why it is relevant to care about future cyber security already today.
- Finding cyber security solutions that will tackle (future) energy system security challenges.
- An open innovation approach: Creating mutual benefit between cyber security startups and an energy corporate.
- Examples of use cases and proof of concepts

Panelists

Shahid Raza / Director of Cyber Security Unit / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Alexandru Mitea / Co-Founder & CEO / Green Energy Allies

Paul Jenkinson / Cyber Security, IT Strategy and Architecture Director / RES Renewable Norden Ab

19:15 Chairman's Closing Remarks and End of Day Two

Conference Speakers

Agis Digkas / Vice-President of BoD / Renewable Energy Sources Operator & Guarantees of Origin – DAPEEP SA

Agis Digkas serves as Executive Vice President of Greece's Renewable Energy Sources Operator, a state owned company that is responsible for Renewable Energy Market of Greece. The company is the largest shareholder in the Hellenic Energy Exchange (HEEx), the second largest seller after Public Power Company and the auctioneer of the CO2 Emissions Allowances in Greece. In this capacity, he oversees and coordinates the strategic development of Greece's Renewable Energy Market, increasing penetration and ensuring sustainability of existing and new RES & CHP investments. He represents the company to European & International Institutions, strengthening government's effort to tackle climate change and its consequences. Prior to this, Agis worked as an energy consultant with a demonstrated history in both private and public sector. He studied Mechanical Engineering at National Technical University of Athens and holds an MBA and a PhD in "Decision Support Systems & Systemic Risk Analysis" from University of Athens.

Alexandru Mitea / Co-Founder & CEO / Green Energy Allies

Hi, I am Alexandru Mitea and I am responsible with the business development of GEA. I have a Bachelors and Masters in Architecture from Architectural Association School of Architecture in London, UK. Qualified architect specialized in reuse of building materials and readaptation of existing structures to improve their energy grading. Previously worked in international architecture offices in Rotterdam, Vienna and London.

Anjos Nijk / Managing Director / European Network for Cyber Security (ENCS)

Anjos Nijk is managing director of the European Network for Cyber Security (ENCS). In addition to his duties with ENCS, he is a member of the steering committee of the Smart Grids Task Force of the European Commission Directorate-General for Energy, a member of the Cyber Security Expert Group and ENCS liaison with European associations including EDSO, ENTSO-E and EUTC.

Carlo Corsaro / MLOps Lead / H2Go Power

Carlo Corsaro is a PhD in Atmospheric Physics from Imperial College London. After co-founding Rediscovery.io, a Data Science startup focused on Computer Vision solutions, he moved on to become the CTO of Predina, a tech start-up using AI to predict the risk of having traffic collisions based on contextual factors. After Predina, he joined the Machine Learning team at H2GO Power as the MLOps Lead. He's currently working on the development of HyAI, a cloud-based software service that uses state-of-the-art machine learning and optimisation algorithms to make intelligent, data-driven decisions that maximise the monetisation of hydrogen systems.

Florian Lütticken / Team Lead OT Renewable Generation / EnBW – Energie Baden – Württemberg AG

EMPLOYMENT

EnBW AG - Operations Renewable Energies Stuttgart, DE

2019 - now Team Lead OT & IT Renewables Energies
2013 - 2019 Engineer Process and Control Technology Renewable Energies

EnBW Kraftwerke AG - Engineering Power Plants Stuttgart, DE

2010 - 2013 Project Engineer Power Plant Control Technology

EDUCATION

KIT - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Universität of Karlsruhe) Karlsruhe, DE

2004 - 2010 Degree in Electrical Engineering & Information Technology

Conference Speakers

Ayat-allah Bouramdane / Group Leader "Climate Change – Energy" / Green Energy Park (GEP), Research Institute for Solar Energy and New Energies (IRESEN)

Biography Born in 1995, Dr. Ayat-allah Bouramdane completed her Engineer's degree in Renewable Energy at the School of Energy Engineering of the International University of Rabat (UIR), in 2017, in Morocco, with thesis on the implementation of different structure of hybrid systems in different regions of Morocco at the Green Energy Park (GEP) of the Research Institute for Solar Energy and New Energies (IRESEN). In 2016, Ayat-allah had the opportunity to participate in an exchange program where she spent six months at the European School of Materials Engineering (EEIGM) and the National School of Electricity and Mechanics (ENSEM) of the University of Lorraine in Nancy, France. Thereafter, in 2018, Ayat-allah completed her master in Energy & Environment: Science Technology & Management (STEEM) at Ecole Polytechnique (IX) in Palaiseau, France, with a thesis on the operation of photovoltaic power plants (data processing and analysis, modeling and faults diagnosis) at the Group of Electrical Engineering – Paris – CentraleSupélec (GeePs). These experiences inspired Ayat-allah to contribute to a transition towards a greener future. In 2021, Ayat-allah obtained her Ph.D. degree from the Institut Polytechnique de Paris (IP Paris, particularly at IX, Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique - Institut Pierre simon Laplace "LMDIPSL"), on a thesis titled "Scenarios of Large-Scale Solar Integration with Wind in Morocco: Impact of Storage, Cost, Spatio-Temporal Complementarity and Climate Change". Her thesis research also led to a number of peer-reviewed publications and conference participation as speaker. Ayat-allah also contributed to the development of a Python software for climate-aware renewable energy mixes in Morocco. This work was conducted in the framework of the Energy4Climate Interdisciplinary Center (E4C) of IP Paris and Ecole des Ponts ParisTech, supported by MED-OCEAN research contract. Ayat-allah currently holds a position as a postdoctoral researcher and department leader at the GEP, IRESEN, UM6P. In April 2022, Ayat-allah has created the group "Climate Change - Energy", known as RTP4EREES whose objective is to offer multidimensional solutions to move 2 towards a climate-resilient energy transition. Indeed, the group offers an approach focused on (i) research, (ii) training and (iii) recommendations to the national energy strategy, hence the name "Research - Teaching - Politics (RTP)". The specific objective of the RTP4EREES group is the sizing, modeling and optimization of current and future energy systems in several regions of the world and more specifically in Morocco to meet the electricity consumption in the most (i) economical way, with (ii) a low risk of production-demand inadequacy and the most (iii) environmental way, hence the name "Economic-Reliable-Environmental Energy Systems (EREES)". The research interests of Ayat-allah lie in the fields of renewable energies (photovoltaic, concentrated solar power and wind), energy flexibility (particularly thermal and battery storage, spatio-temporal complementarity, microgrids) and climate variability/change

Frank Brech / CEO / EnBW Cyber Security GmbH

From 1992 till 2006, Frank Brech has held various management positions at Vodafone Germany and was responsible for the site-acquisition and rollout of the GSM- and UMTS-sites. At GA-Com and H&R Communication he was then responsible for the growth of the mobile communication service unit as head of mobile communication and managing director in Germany, Austria and Turkey. From 2009 till 2019, he developed the telecommunication / broadband business at EnBW and was one of the founders of NetCom BW. Since November 2019, Frank has been responsible for the EnBW innovation project „Full Kritis Service“, which has been spun off into the EnBW Cyber Security GmbH.

Jordi Cuijarro / CyberSecurity Innovation Director / Fundació i2CAT

Jordi Guijarro is working as the Cybersecurity Innovation Director at i2CAT. With more than 20 years in ICT sector, he is an expert in cloud oriented and cybersecurity services. In the cybersecurity arena he has experience in managing CERT/CSIRT teams employing proactive, reactive and value-added security services such as perimeter protection, infrastructure hardening, intrusion/anomaly detection, incident handling, etc. He also combines his work at i2CAT with the participation in European and national projects, and collaborates in high education programs with some universities (UPC, UOC, VIU). He obtained his bachelor in Computing Engineering at the Open University of Catalonia (UOC) and a Master in ICT Management at Universitat Ramon Llull (URL).

Conference Speakers

Kim Elman / Director Center for Cyber Security / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Kim Elman is the director of Center for cyber security at RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. He has an extensive background from cyber security and influence operations, often acting as trusted advisor or keynote speaker on hybrid threat topics.

Sachan Manish / Cyber Security Lead / Wood Plc

Cyber Security and IT Risk professional with over 11 years of experience with Petroleum, Banking and Retail industries. Specializes in security tools, technologies, and best practices in IT, OT and Cloud environments with focus on Governance, Risk, Compliance management and User awareness.

Mihai Mladin / Head of Projects Department / Romanian Energy Center

Currently Head of Projects Department within Romanian Energy Center, Mihai has a large experience of over 15 years in management consulting, EU funding and technical assistance projects, holding the positions of manager and senior consultant in a multinational, cross-industry environment. He is certified in Project Management and Business Process Management, having an extensive experience as Project Manager and Senior Advisor in the implementation of 11 large international energy research projects, funded through the H2020 and ERASMUS programs, but also in several transnational and cross-industry management consultancy projects, business development activities and administration of state aid schemes. The area of expertise and involvement in research projects is mainly aimed at the coordination of the work packages on business modelling, economic impact assessment, dissemination, exploitation of the project results, policies, and regulations.

Neda Maria Kaizumi / VP Quality & Business Excellence / Freyr Clean Battery Solutions

SKILLS

Global certified auditor for last 20 years
Technical inspector for fire safety, security systems and technical installations
Strong global leader
Strong financial transformer
Result driver
Strong communication skills with broad network
Strong negotiations skills
Strategic planner
Future oriented with strong sustainability and digitization focus

EDUCATION

Industrial Safety (Fire safety system) engineer
Masters of International Management
Masters of Philosophy
PhD in conflict resolutions
Currently studying Business Analytics in Harvard Business School

WORK EXPERIENCE

Experience working in Refinery with Fire Safety systems
Experience in United Nations as COO
Experience from Oslo International College as COO
Experience from Motorola Solutions as HSSE Manager
Experience from Aker Solutions as HSSEQ Manager
Experience with Technical Installation in Caverion as Head of HSSEQ and Sustainability
Now, VP Quality in Scatec

Conference Speakers

Nikolaos Anagnostou / Senior Asset Performance / Engineer Glennmont Partners

Nikolaos (Nik) Anagnostou is Senior Performance Engineer at Glennmont Partners, one of the largest renewable energy fund managers in Europe. He has 16+ years of global experience in renewables including asset and project management, engineering, construction, operations, and technical advisory and due diligence consulting. Since joining Glennmont Partners, he has managed 35+ utility scale wind and solar plants across Europe. Nowadays he manages performance analytics, asset management systems, and cybersecurity for Glennmont's fleet of operating assets. He is passionate about climate change and the energy transition. He studied Electrical and Computer Engineering at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, and holds an MSc in Computer and Internet Technologies from the University of Strathclyde in Glasgow.

Panayiotis Nicolaidis / Project & Maintenance Engineer / Green Energy Group

Contact: refpanayiotisnicolaidis@gmail.com, 00447470058381, 0035799883739,

LinkedIn: Panayiotis Nicolaidis.

Exceedingly motivated electrical and electronics engineer, with a career in the renewable industry. Highly experienced in Power Electronics, Electrical Installations and Renewable Energy Projects. Ambitious individual, that is characterized by a high level of professionalism, with a tendency of being perfectionist, along with showing leadership skills. Very cooperative and motivating person, within a team. Always keen to learn new things and ideas.

Paul Jenkinson / Cyber Security, IT Strategy and Architecture Director / RES Renewable Norden Ab

Paul is a highly experienced senior IT leader and security professional having spent over 20 years in a variety of roles involving information security, cyber operations, data networks, enterprise architecture, risk management, IT governance and compliance. Paul operated in many environments of dynamic business change where there's a constant need to evolve technology solutions and cyber resilience measures to drive and deliver successful business outcomes. Paul has led and overseen numerous change initiatives in the Energy sector covering digital, technology and cyber security transformation. Paul is currently the Cyber Security, Architecture and Strategy Director at Renewable Energy Systems (RES) and is globally responsible for the strategy, design and execution of cyber security, operational technology and architecture across RES's diverse portfolio of services. RES is the world's largest independent renewable energy company and is active in onshore and offshore wind, solar, energy storage, green hydrogen, transmission and distribution. As an industry innovator for over 40 years, RES has delivered more than 23GW of renewable energy projects across the globe and supports an operational asset portfolio exceeding 9GW worldwide for a large client base.

Richard Knowlton / Director of Security Studies / Oxford cyber academy

Richard Knowlton is Director of Security Studies at the Oxford Cyber Academy. He is also a visiting lecturer at the University of Cambridge Judge Business School, the Vienna University of Economics and Business (WU), and the University of the West Indies. He is a Fellow of the Institute of Strategic Risk Management (ISRM) and an honorary Life Member of the International Security Management Association (ISMA). Richard spent six years as Group Corporate Security Director of Vodafone, one of the world's major telecommunications companies. He had earlier held the role in Milan of Head of Security (Global Operations) for the Italian UniCredit Group, the largest bank in Central and Eastern Europe. Between 2014-2017, Richard was Executive Director (Europe) for the non-profit Internet Security Alliance (ISA), a multi-sector trade association based in Washington DC. He is a former Board member of the Commonwealth Cyber Crime Consortium. In his earlier career, Richard served in the UK Diplomatic Service, with overseas postings in Europe, Africa, the Middle East, and the Americas. Richard has spoken on digital security risk management on the BBC and regularly presents at major international events, such as the Mobile World Congress in Barcelona. He is the three-times chairman of the annual Security of Things World Conferences in Berlin. Richard is a dual Italian-British citizen and lives in Italy.

Conference Speakers

River Providence / Founder and Director / Crown Green Energy Services

River Providence is the Founder and Director of Crown Green Energy Services, an energy and environmental risk consulting firm specialising in renewable energy and energy efficiency interventions in the CARICOM sub-region. She has been a Climate Change Mitigation and Sustainability Consultant since 2017. She holds an MSc. in Climate Change Management and Finance from Imperial College London, and a BSc. in Energy and Environmental Physics and Mathematics (double) from the University of the West Indies, Mona. Prior to founding Crown Green Energy, she worked as an investment analyst at Camco Clean Energy where she designed and implemented small-island-focused projects and platforms to increase renewable energy integration in emerging markets. She has worked as an environmental risk consultant in the Caribbean for UNICEF, the United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction, and the Caribbean Disaster Emergency Management Agency. She has accumulated years of project management, clean technology investment and project structuring experience for multi-million-dollar funds and platforms in developing nations. She has designed, structured, originated, and fundraised for facilities valued at over USD 850 million, with a focus on the Caribbean clean energy sector.

Shahid Raza / Director of Cyber Security Unit / RISE Research Institutes of Sweden

Shahid Raza is the Director of Cybersecurity at RISE where he leads a team of 20+ technical security experts, half of them have PhD in cybersecurity. He is also the founder and leader of RISE Cyber Range, a unique cybersecurity test and demo arena in Sweden. Shahid is a cybersecurity expert and holds a Master of Science and a PhD degree, both in cybersecurity. Shahid is also an Associate Professor in Uppsala University where he has four PhD students as the main supervisor.

Shikhar Manocha / Technical Project Manager / Promondis Energy GmbH

Shikhar recently joined Promondis Energy GmbH as the technical project manager to execute his skills in the project management of renewable energy technologies, especially solar PV. Immediately prior to this job, he worked with an Irish renewable energy consultancy for 2 years to establish the foundation of the company. Shikhar holds a master's degree in Sustainable Energy & Green Technologies, Galileo Master Certificate in Solar Photovoltaic and a bachelor's degree in Electrical and Electronics engineering. Shikhar's expertise in the Solar PV industry ranges from resource assessment & system design to the project implementation & asset management phase.

Stefan Deutscher / Partner and Associate Director, Global Topic Leader for Cybersecurity & IT Infrastructure Operations / Boston Consulting Group

Stefan A. Deutscher is a core member of BCG's Technology Advantage and Technology, Media & Telecommunications practices. He is BCG's global topic leader for cybersecurity and IT risk management, as well as BCG's global topic leader for IT infrastructure and data center operations, and he often supports his clients also at the cross-roads of these two topics. Stefan works on these topics across industries since joining BCG in 2001 and serves clients on all continents, from insurance, banking, aerospace, media, industrial goods, mining and chemical industries, to IT and telecommunications companies and public sector organizations. Since 2016, Stefan also serves as a Project Advisor to the World Economic Forum on the topic of "Advancing Cyber Resilience". His work is focused on empowering boards and executive teams with tools and practices to identify and manage business risks emanating from cyber threats, on enabling public-private collaboration around cyber resilience, and on the cyber resilience in heavily ecosystemed industries. Before joining BCG, Stefan spent nearly ten years building, operating, and advising academic computing centers, while also teaching and conducting research in computational atomic and surface physics, quantum chemistry, and high-performance computing at several international research centers in the US, France, Spain, and Austria. As a byproduct he speaks several languages.

Conference Speakers

Stuart Okin / Deputy Director for Cyber Regulation & Digital Services / Ofgem

Stuart Okin – Ofgem (UK Energy Regulator) - Deputy Director for Cyber Regulation & Digital Services

Stuart started in software development, moving into technology, infrastructure and Cyber. He was previously the Microsoft Chief Information Security Advisor and was also an Accenture Partner, leading the technology consulting practice. He has been with Ofgem (the UK Energy Regulator) for 4 years – building the Cyber team, with a focus on Network & Information Systems (NIS) regulatory guidance, engagement, reporting and inspections, as well as Price control cyber resilience investment allocation to the sector. Stuart is also responsible for Ofgem Digital Services – who are responsible for Ofgem infrastructure, endpoint and Scheme platforms at Ofgem, distributing £10b to UK consumers a year.

Toni Sulankivi / Head of Cyber Security / Tiko Energy Solutions

Toni Sulankivi is the Head of Cyber Security at tiko Energy Solutions AG. He has extensive experience in mission critical infrastructures both in private and governmental sectors, including e.g. nuclear, defense, transportation, telco and cloud service provider environments. He excels in managing the big picture of cyber security designs and strategy, and thrives to build more secure and sustainable future for everyone.

Toralf Nitsch / CEO / GE4ABV

After more than 25 years activities in the financial sector I did put my focus on consulting and green energy works and brought some disruptive innovations to make the world a little better.

- **November 2018**
COO at Rinovasol.com, Weiden, Germany. The leading company for refurbishing, reparation and recycling of Solar Modules.
- **2018**
COO at rePOWERPARTNER.com, Netherlands. Creating a world of cheap, liable energy produced by refurbished solar panels on a global scale.
- **2016**
UPWEGO.info at United Energy Group B.V. Durable Mobility within a Circular Economy. Why a Mix of UBER, AirBNB and DELL is a disruptive instrument for the existing car industry - how to motivate people to think new about their mobility.
- **2015**
Baseload Buster at Sun Invention Innovations B.V., Amsterdam. Only plug-in and save money. The worlds FIRST AC Battery to reduce the permanent consumption in your house. Full solar powered.
- **2012**
Plug&Save - Balcony Power Plants at Sun Invention Ltd, London. The world FIRST AC solar panel with storage onboard. New regulations had been introduced in Germany after we did enter the market.
- **2010**
German Electric – Electric Car at Jinan Dragon Investment Consulting Co., Ltd., Jinan - China. I was the officer in charge for a car transformation from petrol powered into electric.

Troels Rahbek Lindhard / Lead Consultant / Peak Wind

Troels Rahbek Lindhard is a Lead Consultant with PEAK Wind within (OT) SCADA and cyber security. He has more than 11 years of experience in the renewable industry, working across a range of commercial and technical functions. Troels has previously worked as a Head of SCADA & Security at a major renewable operator.

Conference Speakers

Zoya Pourmirza / Senior Research Associate / Newcastle University

Dr Pourmirza is the lead of the Security and Resilience theme at the Centre for Energy at Newcastle. She works with the National Centre for Energy Systems Integration (CESI) and Active Building Centre (ABC), investigating energy systems digitalisation with the focus on ICT design, data communication efficiency, and cybersecurity. She is the Principal Investigator (PI) for the "Energy Systems Digitalisation" project, working with international partners, and the PI for the EPSRC IAA project "Digitalisation and Digital Twinning of Energy Systems" collaborating with Energy Systems Catapult in the UK. Previously, she was involved in the UK Research and Innovation Infrastructure Roadmap as the lead researcher to identify the current landscape and future key research infrastructure for the energy sector, to inform policy makers in order to meet the UK Government 2050 carbon targets. She also served as a policy advisor for the UK Government working on cybersecurity framework for EV chargepoints, to inform policy and relevant standards and regulatory approaches.

**Renewable Energy
Cyber Security Forum**

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Berlin | Germany**